

ORTHO-SUBSTITUTED DIPHENYLS. PART IV. A NEW SYNTHESIS OF PHENANTHRENE

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o-Phenyl- α : β -dibromocinnamic acid and *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene have been prepared. The latter on treatment with aluminium chloride produces phenanthrene. The yield of phenanthrene is much improved if zinc chloride, instead of aluminium chloride, is used as a condensing agent. On treatment with alcoholic potassium hydroxide *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene gives a high yield of *o*-diphenylacetylene of silver acetylide which has also been prepared.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 181) the authors have already reported the preparation of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid and *o*-phenyl- α : β -dichlorocinnamic acid, the latter by the loss of a molecule each of carbon dioxide and hydrochloric acid gave *o*-phenyl- ω -chlorostyrene which formed the starting point for a new synthesis of phenanthrene. The authors have now succeeded in obtaining the corresponding bromine derivative; the *o*-phenyl- α : β -dibromocinnamic acid being obtained by the addition of a molecule of bromine to a chloroformic solution of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid. *o*-Phenyl- α : β -dibromocinnamic acid, a colourless, crystalline and stable compound, readily loses on treatment with Na_2CO_3 solution (moderately conc.) a molecule each of carbon dioxide and hydrobromic acid to give the corresponding *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene, a light straw coloured oil, readily distillable under reduced pressure. It has been noticed that the loss of carbon dioxide and hydrohalogen acid by the treatment with sodium carbonate solution takes place much more readily in the case of the dibromo compound than with the dichloro-acid. The *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene on treatment with aluminium chloride in the usual manner gives a good yield of phenanthrene. The production of phenanthrene from the chloro- as well as the bromostyrenes clearly indicates the structure of these halogen compounds; in their production from the dihalogen acid by the action of sodium carbonate, it is the α -halogen and the β -hydrogen atoms which are removed.

Condensing agents other than aluminium chloride have been tried; a far better yield (nearly 70%) of phenanthrene has been obtained when anhydrous zinc chloride is used; the quantity of plastic byproduct is also very much reduced.

If, however, the removal of the halogen acid is carried out with the help of potassium hydroxide, no ring-closure leading to the formation of phenanthrene is observed. Alkalis therefore remove the halogen acid only from the side-chain with the formation of polymerised products (whose nature has not yet been closely investigated) if solid potassium hydroxide is used and of considerable quantity of *o*-diphenylacetylene on heating with alcoholic potash.

The *o*-phenyl- ω -halogenostyrenes therefore suffer the loss of a molecule of the halogen acid in two different ways: firstly with the help of metallic chlorides like aluminium and zinc chloride where the *ortho*-halogen atom of the second

aromatic nucleus is lost along with the terminal halogen atom of the ethylenic side-chain, leading to the formation of tricyclic aromatic hydrocarbon, pheanthrene, and secondly with the agency of caustic alkalis when the reaction is confined to the side-chain and leads either to polymerised products or to the formation of the acetylene derivatives by the removal of a molecule of the corresponding halogen acid.

This behaviour is also in agreement with the general observation that halogen derivatives of ethylenic compounds are usually not found to yield the acetylenic compounds by the loss of a molecule of halogen acid through the agency of aluminium chloride. The method adopted in the preparation of *o*-diphenylacetylene follows closely that described by Manchot (*Annalen*, 1912, 387, 283). Gilman's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 425; "Organic Synthesis", II, p. 67) for the preparation of phenylacetylene is not found satisfactory for the preparation of *o*-diphenylacetylene. When solid potassium hydroxide is used, the final hydrocarbon obtained is undistillable and remains unidentified, although a large quantity of halogen acid is generated (90% as estimated in the form of silver halide in the aqueous extract). On prolonged heating with alcoholic potassium hydroxide a colourless oil, which can be distilled under reduced pressure, is obtained. Dilute alcoholic solution of this compound with ammoniacal silver nitrate solution yields silver acetylide corresponding with the formula $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{C} \equiv \text{C} \cdot \text{Ag}$ and not with $2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{C} \equiv \text{C} \cdot \text{Ag}) + \text{Ag}_2\text{O}$ as given by Glasser (*Annalen*, 1870, 154, 167) for the corresponding silver compound of acetylene. The silver acetylide obtained from *o*-diphenylacetylene is white when freshly precipitated but becomes red on exposure to light.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

o-Phenyl- α : β -dibromocinnamic Acid.—To a suspension of well powdered *o*-phenylcinnamic acid (11.2g., 1/20 mol.) in dry chloroform (112 g.) was gradually added a solution of bromine (8 g., 1/20 mol.) in dry chloroform (80 c.c.). The solution which was surrounded by cold water, was well shaken after each addition of bromine. Considerable amount of heat was generated during the absorption of bromine and the suspension went completely in solution. The solution was kept overnight when part of the *o*-phenyl- α : β -dibromocinnamic acid was precipitated as heavy granules. This was filtered off and a further quantity recovered by distilling off chloroform. On crystallisation from benzene, colourless granular crystals were obtained, m.p. 171°. yield 17 g. (89%). (Found: Br, 41.2%. $C_{15}H_{23}O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 41.67 per cent).

o-Phenyl- ω -bromostyrene.—The above acid (13 g., 1/30 mol.) on being added to 100 c. c. of sodium carbonate solution (3.5 g., 1/30 mol.) gave a clear alkaline solution. This solution, however, soon became turbid and on standing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the turbidity disappeared and an oil was produced. It was refluxed on the water-bath for an hour at the end of which the production of the oil was complete. After cooling, the oil was extracted with ether and dried overnight with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was evaporated and the residue on being further distilled under reduced pressure gave an oily product, b. p. 157°/0.5 mm., yield 8.2 g. (93%). (Found: Br, 30.6. $C_{14}H_{11}Br$ requires Br, 30.88 per cent).

Phenanthrene (with aluminium chloride).—Well powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.27 g., 1/500 mol.) was gradually added to freshly distilled *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene (5.20 g., 1/50 mol.) contained in a dry flask, fitted with an air-condenser. The flask was then placed in a water-bath whose temperature was slowly raised to boiling point. At 55° a vigorous reaction occurred suddenly and the contents darkened considerably with the evolution of a large amount of gas. Heating was continued and the flask was kept in boiling water for an hour at the end of which evolution of hydrobromic acid ceased completely. The dark mass was treated with ice-cold water and on being removed from the sides of the flask it assumed a yellow colour. It was extracted with ether and dried overnight with fused calcium chloride. The ether was distilled off and the residue on being distilled under reduced pressure gave an oil, b. p. 144°/0.5 mm., which solidified into colourless crystals on cooling. The solid on crystallisation from 70% alcohol gave shining flakes of phenanthrene, m. p. 99°, yield 1.4 g. (39%). The picrate prepared by the usual method melted at 145°. (Found: C, 59.15; H, 2.19. Calc for $C_{20}H_{13}O_7N_3$: C, 58.97; H, 3.19 per cent). The regenerated phenanthrene had m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 94.47; H, 5.46. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}$: C, 94.39; H, 5.62 per cent). The identity of phenanthrene and its picrate was confirmed by mixed m.p. with a specimen of pure (Schuchardt) phenanthrene and its picrate.

Phenanthrene (with zinc chloride).—Well powdered anhydrous zinc chloride (2.7 g., 1/50 mol.) was gradually added to freshly distilled *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene

(5.2 g., 1/50 mol.) contained in a dry flask fitted with an air-condenser. The flask was kept in an oil-bath whose temperature was gradually raised. At 175° (bath temperature) vapours of hydrogen bromide started escaping from the top of the condenser. The oil-bath was then maintained at 180° for 5 hours and the flask was well shaken at frequent intervals. After 5 hours the evolution of hydrobromic acid ceased completely and the heating was stopped. After cooling, the contents were given a similar treatment as in the previous case and shining flakes of phenanthrene (m.p. 99.5°) were obtained, yield 2.6 g (72.4%). The picrate melted at 144°. (Found : C, 59.20 ; H, 2.69. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{13}O_7N_3$: C 59.97 ; H, 3.19 per cent). The regenerated phenanthrene melted at 100°. (Found : C, 94.49 ; H, 5.4. Calc for $C_{14}H_{10}$: C, 94.39 ; H, 5.62 per cent). The identity of phenanthrene and its picrate was established as in the previous case.

Similarly well powdered anhydrous zinc chloride (2.7g., 1/50 mol.) and *o*-phenyl- α -chlorostyrene (4.3 g., 1/50 mol.) were heated together for 5 hours at 200°. The resulting product on being treated as in the previous case produced a high yield (2.4 g., 67%) of phenanthrene. The picrate melted at 144°. (Found : C 59.18 ; H, 2.98. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{13}O_7N_3$: C, 59.97 ; H, 3.19 per cent). The regenerated phenanthrene melted at 100°. The identity of phenanthrene and its picrate was established in the usual manner.

o-Diphenylacetylene.—Freshly distilled *o*-phenyl- α -bromostyrene (5g., 1/52 mol.), absolute alcohol (3.1g., 1/15 mol.) and pellets of pure potassium hydroxide (3.8 g., 1/15 mol.) were taken in a dry flask fitted with a condenser. The flask was kept in an oil-bath which was gradually heated and maintained at 125° while the flask was shaken frequently. The contents were heated at this temperature for 3 hours after which no more potassium bromide appeared to separate. After cooling, ice-cold water was added and the oil produced was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was left overnight with calcium chloride. The ether was evaporated and the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave an oil, b. p. 137°/3 mm., not solidifying on cooling, yield 2.45 g. (71.3%). (Found : C, 94.66 ; H 5.31. $C_{14}H_{10}$ requires C, 94.39 ; H 5.62 per cent).

Silver Compound of o-Diphenylacetylene.—When a very dilute solution of *o*-diphenylacetylene in alcohol was mixed with an excess of an ammoniacal solution of silver nitrate, a turbidity was immediately produced and tiny bubbles of gas (hydrogen) were evolved. The mixture was well shaken and kept aside for 14 minutes, at the end of which a large amount of white precipitate deposited at the bottom. The precipitate was filtered at the pump, washed first with an ammoniacal water, then with alcohol and finally with absolute ether. It was dried to a constant weight in a vacuum desiccator and the composition determined by ignition. (Found : Ag 37.72. $C_{14}H_{10}$, Ag requires Ag, 37.88 per cent).